

ISic0006

Funerary inscription for Gaius Iulius Felix and Appuleia Rogata

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cossura

Place of origin (modern)

Pantelleria

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3506

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C (aius) · Iulius · Felix
2. vixit · ann (is)
3. Appuleia · Rogata
4. vixit · ann (is)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Gaius Iulis Felix lived for [--] years. Appuleia Rogata lived for [--] years

Translation (it)

Gaio Giulio Felice visse anni [--]. Appuleia Rogata visse anni [--]

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491874

EDCS 22100631

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7512 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 6

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